

COMPLICATIONS OF EMERGENCY OBSTETRIC HYSTERECTOMY AMONG WOMEN PRESENTING AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Dr. Mizna Memon^{*1}, Dr. Sofia Butt², Dr. Rozeena³, Dr. Faryal⁴, Dr. Baby Safiya⁵,
Dr. Ushna⁶

^{*1,3,4,5}Postgraduate Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Civil Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Civil Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

⁶Postgraduate Trainee (MPhil), Department of Pharmacology, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, Pakistan

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20608391>

Keywords

Acute Kidney Injury, Hysterectomy, Postpartum Hemorrhage, Placenta Accreta Spectrum

Article History

Received: 06 May 2025

Accepted: 18 June 2025

Published: 14 July 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Mizna Memon

Abstract

Objective: To determine the complications in patients undergoing Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy patients in Karachi.

Material and Methods: Cross-sectional study was carried out from 13th October 2024 to 13th April 2025 at the tertiary care hospital in Karachi. Women aged 18-49 years who underwent emergency obstetric hysterectomy were included through non-random consecutive sampling technique. Sample size of 191 was calculated using online open-epi sample size calculator using anticipated frequency of mortality at 14.4%, confidence level at 95% and margin of error at 5%. Patients were inquired about their socio-demographic and clinical details. Data related to procedural indications and post-surgical complications were recorded.

Results: Placenta Accreta Spectrum (39.8%) and uterine rupture (35.6%) were observed as the primary indications for EOH. Whereas, the women in this study suffered substantial morbidity, including AKI (25.7%), sepsis (20.0%), and DIC (15.7%). The overall mortality rate was 3.1%. Massive blood transfusion (aOR 4.25) and pre-existing hypertension (aOR 2.81) are the independent predictors for AKI. Moreover, co-morbidities including obesity (aOR 3.05) and diabetes (aOR 2.88), were found as the independent predictors for sepsis. Furthermore, the development of DIC was the most powerful independent predictor of mortality (aOR 18.5, p=0.009)

Conclusion: The study concludes that uterine rupture and accreta are the main indications for EOH. Blood transfusion along with hypertension serves as the major cause for AKI development. DIC is developed as the direct consequence of uterine rupture with severe blood loss.

INTRODUCTION:

Emergency obstetric hysterectomy (EOH), the surgical removal of the uterus at the time of vaginal delivery (VD) or delivery through caesarean section (CS) or in the immediate postpartum period.⁽¹⁾ It is crucial that this be avoided as much as possible because EOH is typified by the conundrum of having to decide between preserving a life and sacrificing fertility.⁽²⁾ Though the incidence of EOH is relatively low, ranging from 0.2 to 5 per 1,000

deliveries, it is linked with significant maternal morbidity and mortality. The procedure represents a failure of conservative management and is often performed under emergent, physiologically challenging circumstances.^(3,4) The primary indications for EOH have evolved over the past decades. While uterine atony was historically the leading cause, recent evidence from tertiary centres worldwide points to a rising incidence of abnormal placentation, particularly Placenta Accreta Spectrum (PAS), as the

dominant indication. This shift is largely attributed to the global increase in caesarean delivery rates. Other major indications include uterine rupture, which is catastrophic, and extensions of uterine incisions during caesarean sections.^(4, 5)

EOH is fraught with complications, including massive blood transfusion (MBT), injury to the urinary tract, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), sepsis, acute kidney injury (AKI), and admission to the intensive care unit (ICU).^(6, 7) Identifying the patient-specific factors that independently predict them is crucial for clinical preparedness, patient counselling, and resource allocation in tertiary care settings. The incidence of EOH tends to be higher in low and lower-middle income countries that is 1.1 per 1000 births and 3 per 1000 births respectively. The high-income countries reported with the lowest incidence 0.7 per 1,000 births.⁽⁸⁾ In Pakistan, the incidence of EOH is increased in last decade. Recent Pakistani studies have reported the incidence of EOH in Pakistan varies from 11 to 13 per 1,000 deliveries.^(9, 10) The global indications for EOH differ between developed and developing nations like Pakistan. The most common reasons for EOH include uterine rupture, placenta accreta spectrum, uterine atony, placental abruption, placenta previa, unexplained bleeding, cervical tear or extension of uterine incision, wide ligament hematoma, and infection.⁽¹¹⁾ Even though the EOH saved their lives, these patients still need to be continuously watched to avoid consequences such wound infection, renal failure, shock, septicemia, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), and death.⁽¹²⁾ This technique needs to be given the utmost attention because it is becoming more common due to the rise in irreversible causes of life-threatening hemorrhage, improper placentation, and uterine rupture. This will be crucial in reducing maternal mortality.⁽¹³⁾ While international data exists, there is a need for contemporary regional data that reflects local obstetric practices and patient populations. Keeping in view the paucity of data, this study aims to address this gap by determining the complications of EOH and identifying the independent predictors of severe morbidity among women presenting to a major tertiary care hospital in Karachi, Pakistan. Therefore,

this study was designed to determine the complications in patients undergoing Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy patients in Karachi.

METHODS AND MATERIAL:

This Cross-Sectional Study was conducted at the department and Gynaecology, Dow University of Health Sciences / Civil Hospital, Karachi 13th October 2024 to 13th April 2025 after getting approval from the CPSP. Participants aged between 18-49 years, and those undergoing the emergency hysterectomy irrespective to indication were included while those with uterine fibroid, cervical cancer, immunocompromised women with HIV, under chemotherapeutic surgery and those with organ transplant taking some medications were excluded from the study. Sample size was calculated using WHO sample size calculator. By using proportion of mortality in women undergoing EOH 14.4%⁽⁹⁾, margin of error 5% and confidence level 95%. The required sample size for this study is 190. The participants were selected through non-random consecutive sampling technique. After informing participants / attendants regarding all risk and benefits was explain to patient / attendant (if patient unable to give consent) and written informed consent was taken.

Baseline clinical and demographic details were recorded at the time of enrolment and noted in a pre-designed and pre-tested questionnaire. All procedures were performed by senior consultant (obstetrics and Gynecology) with over 5 years of experience. Post-procedure assessment of complication i.e wound infection, AKI, anemia, UTI, sepsis, massive blood transfusion, ICU admission, DIC and mortality women was recorded. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS version 25. Median and inter-quartile range (IQR) was reported for quantitative variables such as age, family monthly income, duration of procedure and length of hospital stay. While frequency and percentage were used to report qualitative variables such as residence, indication of hysterectomy, diabetes, hypertension, smoking, and complication. Chi-square test was employed for differences in categorical variables while multivariate analysis was performed for controlling confounder and identifying the predictors of severe

complications. P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

This study included 191 women who fulfilled the selection criteria. The median age is 32 years, with the largest group being between 25 and 34

years old. A majority of patients reside in urban areas, but a large minority come from rural settings. Moreover, the median BMI is 28.1 kg/m², which falls into the "overweight" category. A combined majority of patients are either overweight or obese. Over two-third of the patients were without any co-morbidity. (Table1)

Table 1: Socio-Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients (n=191)

Characteristics	n (%)
Age (years), Median (IQR)	32 (28-38)
• < 25 years	41 (21.5%)
• 25 - 34 years	94 (49.2%)
• ≥ 35 years	56 (29.3%)
Residence	
• Urban	117 (61.3%)
• Rural	74 (38.7%)
Family Monthly Income (PKR)	
• < 25,000	88 (46.1%)
• 25,000 - 50,000	73 (38.2%)
• > 50,000	30 (15.7%)
BMI (kg/m²), Median (IQR)	28.1 (24.9-30.8)
• Underweight (<18.5)	4 (2.1%)
• Normal weight (18.5 - 24.9)	65 (34.0%)
• Overweight (25.0 - 29.9)	83 (43.5%)
• Obese (≥ 30.0)	39 (20.4%)
Diabetes	
• Yes	33 (17.3%)
• No	158 (82.7%)
Hypertension	
• Yes	53 (27.7%)
• No	138 (72.3%)
Smoking	
• Yes	16 (8.4%)
• No	175 (91.6%)

Among the indications of EOH, placenta accreta spectrum was the most common indication (n= 76; 39.8%) followed by uterine rupture (n=68; 35.6%) and uterine atony (n= 38; 20.0%). Whereas, n= 9 (4.6%) were reported with other causes. Whereas, concerning procedural details and hospital stay, the median duration of EOH procedure was 145 minutes with IQR of 120-180 minutes. Whereas, median length of stay in the hospital after the EOH was 10 days with IQR of 8-16 days.

Table 2 is presenting the results of EOH procedures which show high levels of maternal health complications after the procedure. The patient group experienced multiple major organ failures with AKI followed by severe sepsis and fatal hematologic failure from DIC. The previous bleeding episode showed its intensity through the fact that over half of patients needed major blood transfusions while nearly half of them required ICU care due to their life-threatening conditions. (Table 2)

Table 2: Frequency of Post-operative Outcomes and Complications (n=191)

Outcome Category & Specific Outcome	n	%
Major Organ Complications / Systemic Failure		
Acute Kidney Injury (AKI)	49	25.7%
Sepsis	38	20.0%
Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation (DIC)	30	15.7%
Hemorrhagic and Anemic Sequelae		
Massive Blood Transfusion	106	55.5%
Anemia (requiring post-operative transfusion)	92	48.2%
Infectious Complications (Localized)		
Wound Infection	34	17.8%
Urinary Tract Infection (UTI)	19	10.0%
Marker of Overall Morbidity / Level of Care		
ICU Admission	77	40.3%
Final Outcome		
Mortality	6	3.1%

A stratified patients characteristic and its statistically significant association with one particular adverse outcome is presented in Table 3. Among the participants, overweight/obese group experienced sepsis at almost twice the rate compared to other groups. The rate of sepsis was observed significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in patients with a BMI ≥ 25 compared to those with a normal or underweight BMI. There was a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the rate of needing a massive blood transfusion as the rate of blood transfusion was extremely high for patients with Uterine Rupture and Placenta Accreta Spectrum compared to Uterine Atony.

A statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the rate of ICU admission was for hypertensive women compared to the non-hypertensive women. Similarly, the rate of wound infection was twice among patients with diabetes compared to their counterparts ($p < 0.05$). A statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the rate of AKI was observed higher in patients who received a massive transfusion. Moreover, among the patients who developed DIC, higher rate of mortality was observed compared to those without DIC ($p < 0.05$). (Table 3)

Table 3: Stratified Analysis of Major Complications (n=191)

Strata	Group	Outcome	Complication		p-value
			Present	Absent	
BMI	Normal/Underweight (<25)	Sepsis (n=38)	9 (13.0%)	60 (87.0%)	0.031
	Overweight/Obese (≥ 25)		29 (23.8%)	93 (76.2%)	
Indication	Uterine Atony	Massive Blood Transfusion (n=106)	11 (29.0%)	27 (71.0%)	<0.001
	Uterine Rupture		46 (67.6%)	22 (32.4%)	
	Placenta Accreta Spectrum		49 (64.5%)	27 (35.5%)	
Hypertension	No	ICU Admission	44 (32.0%)	94 (68.0%)	<0.001
	Yes		33 (62.3%)	20 (37.7%)	
Diabetes	No	Wound Infection	24 (15.3%)	133 (84.7%)	0.035
	Yes		10 (30.3%)	23 (69.7%)	
Massive Blood Transfusion	No	AKI	9 (10.6%)	76 (89.4%)	<0.001
	Yes		40 (37.7%)	66 (62.3%)	
DIC	No	Mortality	1 (0.6%)	160 (99.4%)	<0.001
	Yes		5 (16.7%)	25 (83.3%)	

Table 4 is presenting the multivariate analysis for exploring the predictors of major complications following EOH in this study. The massive hemorrhage is primary driver of DIC whereas, massive blood transfusion was the strongest predictor of DIC. Patients requiring massive blood transfusion had 5.95 times the odds of developing DIC ($p < 0.05$). Compared to uterine atony, uterine rupture is found as the strong predictor of DIC as it increases the risk of DIC by over 3.80 times ($p < 0.05$) whereas, placenta

accreta spectrum showed not statistical significance as additional risk of DIC. Patients who required massive transfusion, experienced AKI at 4.25 times the rate of other patients ($p < 0.05$). Whereas, the odds of AKI for hypertensive patients increased by 2.81 times ($p < 0.05$). The risk of sepsis development in overweight and diabetic patients tripled compared to their counterparts ($p < 0.05$). Overwhelmingly, the strongest predictor of mortality was the development of DIC. (Table 4)

Table 4: Multivariate analysis of Independent Predictors of Major Complications Following EOH

Outcome & Predictor Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio (aOR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Model 1: Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation (DIC) (n=30 cases)			
Massive Blood Transfusion	5.95	2.20 – 16.1	<0.001
Indication for Hysterectomy:			
Uterine Atony	Ref.	–	–
Placenta Accreta Spectrum	1.85	0.55 – 6.21	0.320
Uterine Rupture	3.80	1.15 – 12.5	0.029
Model 2: Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) (n=49 cases)			
Massive Blood Transfusion (Yes vs. No)	4.25	2.01 – 9.01	<0.001
Hypertension (Yes vs. No)	2.81	1.31 – 6.04	0.008
Model 3: Sepsis (n=38 cases)			
BMI (≥ 25 vs. < 25 kg/m ²)	3.05	1.18 – 7.89	0.021
Diabetes (Yes vs. No)	2.88	1.12 – 7.40	0.028
Model 4: Predictors for Mortality (n=6 cases)			
Development of DIC (Yes vs. No)	18.5	2.04 – 167.5	0.009
Development of Sepsis (Yes vs. No)	4.8	0.85 – 27.1	0.076

DISCUSISON:

EOH is an essential intervention for situations of severe intra- or postpartum hemorrhage and other uterine pathologies. It is a major contributor to maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide.⁽¹¹⁾ The frequency of EOH varies greatly between nations and even within institutions. The prevalence of EOH is increasing in areas with few resources, like Pakistan.⁽¹²⁾ With the rising prevalence, the incidences of EOH related complications are also at surge specially in the low to lower middle nations.⁽³⁾ Exploring such complications in the metropolitan city of Karachi, this study selected a high-volume public sector tertiary care facility. We thoroughly examined all complications and risk variables that result in unfavourable outcomes following EOH. In this study, the

median age is 32 years, with the largest group being between 25 and 34 years old. These findings are consistent with studies by Ala et al. And Verma et al reported the major proportion of their study population of same age group.^(8,9) Number of indications for EOH including uterine rupture, placenta accreta spectrum, uterine atony, placental abruption, placenta previa, unspecified hemorrhage, cervical tear or extension of uterine incision, broad ligament hematoma, and sepsis have been reported by several international and national studies.⁽⁸⁻¹⁰⁾ In our study, placenta accreta spectrum was the most common (39.8%) indication followed by uterine rupture (35.6%) and uterine atony (19.9%). The data shows that increasing cesarean section rates have established a global pattern which reshapes how doctors perform

birth procedures in current times. These pathologies are inherently associated with greater surgical complexity and blood loss compared to uterine atony, which likely drives the high complication rates observed.⁽¹⁰⁾

Among the complications in present study, the top three complications demonstrated were AKI (25.7%) which was the most frequent complication of EOH followed by life-threatening sepsis (20.0%) and catastrophic hematologic collapse due to DIC (15.7%). Moreover, over half (55.5%) patients encountered with the massive blood transfusion which is the stark indicator of the severity of hemorrhage encountered while nearly half (40.3%) of them required ICU care due to their life-threatening conditions. In addition to this, patients faced two categories of health problems because of the body's systemic damage and the development of localized infections which included wound infections at a rate of 17.8% and UTIs at 10.0%.^(2, 10, 14, 15)

In the present study, the medical procedure of EOH resulted in severe complications which led to a 3.1% death rate among patients who required this operation because their life was at risk. These findings are consistent with those reported by Kallianidis et al, Kamal et al., and Shaikh et al.⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁷⁾

In the present study, there was a statistically significant ($p=0.0001$) difference in the rate of needing a massive blood transfusion as the rate of blood transfusion was extremely high for patients with Uterine Rupture and Placenta Accreta Spectrum compared to Uterine Atony. These findings are consistent with those reported by Ornaghi et al, Kaloka et al and Chawanpaiboon et al.⁽¹⁸⁻²⁰⁾ Pakistani studies by Kamal et al., Aslam et al. and Irshad et al. also reported that patients with Placenta accreta in their study needed massive rate of blood transfusion.^(17, 21, 22)

EOH leads to AKI as a major complication because the surgery requires treatment of substantial bleeding which led to the surgical procedure. Blood transfusion serves as a vital emergency treatment for severe PPH yet it can create additional risks for AKI through various transfusion reactions and body stress responses.^(19, 22, 23) Similar findings of the regression analysis in our study demonstrated that massive blood transfusion functioned as the

most significant predictor of AKI development because it produced an adjusted odds ratio of 4.25. The clinical process becomes dangerous because severe bleeding results in hypovolemic shock which needs urgent medical intervention that can cause kidney damage through ischemia-reperfusion injuries.

The main strength of this research comes from its focus on high-risk patients at a major tertiary care referral centre because it delivers real-world clinical information about the most dangerous obstetric emergencies. The use of a consecutive sampling method minimizes selection bias, ensuring that the results are representative of the patient population managed at this institution. The study also has several inherent limitations. The single-centred, retrospective design limits generalizability and may be affected by missing data. The multivariate analysis model cannot account for unmeasured variables like surgical timing, their experience or the time delayed from the onset of hemorrhage. Additionally, the mortality analysis is underpowered due to the low event rate.

CONCLUSION:

Our study revealed that uterine rupture and accreta placenta spectrum has become the leading indication for EOH. The predictable patterns identified that AKI emerges from two main factors: massive blood transfusion and pre-existing hypertension. The development of sepsis depends heavily on metabolic health factors including obesity and diabetes. Moreover, uterine rupture and massive blood loss directly lead to DIC development. Medical professionals can perform exact risk evaluations through the use of well-defined outcome categories.

REFERENCES:

Ayele M, Lake ES, Tilahun BD, Alamrew A, Mulugeta C, Mislu E, et al. Incidence, indications, and outcomes of emergency peripartum hysterectomy in Africa: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Heliyon*. 2025;11(13).

- Lavanderos S, Moraga-Arias B, Muñoz-Baeza F, Cifuentes-Espinoza S, Córdova-Padilla V. Safety and clinical outcomes of obstetric hysterectomies in patients treated at a tertiary hospital in Chile. *Revista Colombiana de Obstetricia y Ginecología*. 2025;76(2):4349.
- Mbakwa MR, Tendongfor N, Ngunyi YL, Ngek ESN, Alemkia F, Egbe TO. Indications and outcomes of emergency obstetric hysterectomy; a 5-year review at the Bafoussam Regional Hospital, Cameroon. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*. 2021;21(1):323.
- Elangovan J, Gomathi V, Devi TA. REVIEW OF EMERGENCY OBSTETRIC HYSTERECTOMIES (EOH) AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL IN SOUTH INDIA-A RETROSPECTIVE COHORT STUDY. *Int J Acad Med Pharm*. 2024;6(1):1191-5.
- Desalegn H, Geta A, Nane D. Peripartum hysterectomy: prevalence, indications, maternal outcomes, and associated factors in a 7-year retrospective review at Wolaita Sodo University Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Southern Ethiopia. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*. 2025;25(1):489.
- Shehzadi I, Salam B, Sardar H, Ayub S, Bashir B, Kousar S. Indications and Outcomes of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy at Tertiary Care Hospital. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023;17(11):103-.
- Kumar HA, Naik M, Fatima SA. Emergency Peripartum Hysterectomy (EPH): A Retrospective Study of Indications, Maternal and Perinatal Outcome in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Journal of South Asian Federation of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2024;16(4):393-6.
- Verma A, Sharma G, Kashyap M, Sharma Sr G. A Retrospective Analysis of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy: A Life-Saving Intervention. *Cureus*. 2023;15(10).
- Ala SH, Husain S, Hussain S. Changing Prevalence of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy, Its Indications and Maternal Outcomes Over a 4-year Period at a Tertiary Care Center in Pakistan. *Journal of South Asian Federation of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2023;14(6):690-3.
- Ali M, Memon M, Ghafar B, Memon M, Shaikh S, Chandio F. Emergency obstetrical hysterectomy among post-partum hemorrhage women in Larkana. *LIAQUAT MEDICAL RESEARCH JOURNAL*. 2024;6(2).
- Naseeb S, Dossal A, Rashid S. An Audit of Hysterectomy at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi. *Journal of The Society of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists of Pakistan*. 2021;11(2):95-9.
- Aslam L, Sohail N, Ayyub N, Sarwar A, Gul M, Afzal A. COMPLICATIONS ASSOCIATED WITH EMERGENCY OBSTETRIC HYSTERECTOMY: A TWO-YEAR REVIEW AT LAHORE GENERAL HOSPITAL. *Pakistan Postgraduate Medical Journal*. 2021;32(04):157-9.
- Nigussie J, Girma B, Molla A, Mareg M. Tetanus Toxoid Vaccination Coverage and Associated Factors among Childbearing Women in Ethiopia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *BioMed research international*. 2021;2021(1):5529315.
- Annan JJK, Konney TO, Sam-Awortwi W, Darkwa KA. Emergency hysterectomy in a tertiary care hospital: indications, surgical outcomes and challenges: a 2-year retrospective descriptive cross-sectional study. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2020;37(1).
- Shaikh F. Emergency obstetric hysterectomy at A tertiary care hospital. *Journal of Surgery Pakistan*. 2022;27(1):21-5.

- Kallianidis AF, Rijntjes D, Brobbel C, Dekkers OM, Bloemenkamp KW, Van Den Akker T. Incidence, indications, risk factors, and outcomes of emergency peripartum hysterectomy worldwide: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2023;141(1):35-48.
- Kamal Q, Bibi H, Sahibzada H, Ali A. Frequency of Diseases Requiring Hysterectomy: A Cross Sectional Study at Tertiary Care Hospitals in Peshawar: Frequency of Diseases Requiring Hysterectomy. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences*. 2023;181-4.
- Ornaghi S, Maraschini A, Donati S, Group ROSSW. Characteristics and outcomes of pregnant women with placenta accreta spectrum in Italy: A prospective population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(6):e0252654.
- Kloka JA, Friedrichson B, Jasny T, Blum LV, Choorapoikayil S, Old O, et al. Anaemia and red blood cell transfusion in women with placenta accreta spectrum: an analysis of 38,060 cases. *Scientific reports*. 2024;14(1):4999.
- Chawanpaiboon S, Titapant V, Pooliam J. Factors Related to Blood Transfusions in Pregnant Women Undergoing Caesarean Sections: A 20-year Retrospective Study. *International Journal of Women's Health*. 2025:3511-26.
- Aslam L, Sohail N, Ayyub N, Sarwar A, Shah AA, Afzal A. Risk Factors, Indications and Outcome of Emergency Obstetric Hysterectomy: A study performed at Tertiary Care Hospital. *Pak J Med Health Sci*. 2022;16(7):169-71.
- Irshad T, Jadoon KN, Imtiaz R, Gul R. Frequency of Maternal Morbidities in Patients with Postpartum Hemorrhage and Anemia. *Indus Journal of Bioscience Research*. 2025;3(5):1050-4.
- Thanasa A, Thanasa E, Xydias EM, Kamaretsos E, Kontogeorgis G, Paraoulakis I, et al. Postpartum Hemorrhage-Induced Acute Kidney Injury Following Obstetric Hysterectomy: A Case Report. *Cureus*. 2025;17(3).